

DEVELOPMENT OF FINANCIAL MARKETS THROUGH INNOVATION

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Annotation: In the development of recommendations on the introduction of certain types of financial instruments into circulation in the financial markets of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: innovation, market, potential, financial instruments, financial capital, image.

Today we need to realize that Uzbekistan is becoming an integral part of the world space and the global financial and economic market. In the field of further increasing the capacity of the financial system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, that is, the use of derivative financial instruments as assets that provide replenishment of the subjects of the world financial system, it is necessary for the economy to work and adapt at their request. A separate segment of the financial market is the connection and specific aspects of all sectors of the financial market. Of course, the activities of the financial market are regulated by regulatory bodies and regulatory legal acts of the financial aspects of the state.

The financial market is considered a complex system, the complexity of which is determined by the variety of links between structural elements, the structural diversity of elements. This leads to the variety and differentiation of the elements of the system, the abundance of criteria for their activity. The development of the system through innovation is-the dynamics of the financial market its constantly changing composition of financial assets and their size, they are determined by changes in demand and supply, etc., which ensures the increase and deepening of

the relations of the financial market as a system with the external environment and further improvement of financial asset management will help. The financial market is an open system, since it shares information with the external environment.

Financial innovation is a function of time. Thus, the concept of " financial innovation " is valid only in a period of time determined by the initial and final point of the life cycle of a particular financial innovation. In this regard, financial innovation cannot be considered .

In the general system of innovations, financial innovation can be distinguished, that is, innovation, working in the field of Finance, is divided into crisis innovation and development innovation, as well as financial innovation and any other innovation. In this regard, a financial product or transaction that is new only to a particular financial institution, but has been carried out in other financial institutions for a long time, cannot be considered a financial novelty. The content of financial innovation consists of new financial transactions.

Financial innovation has something (that is, a material form) that is intended for sale in the financial market. Development through financial innovation includes securities, coins made of precious metals, plastic settlement or credit card, bank account agreement, pension policy, real estate object, etc. Financial innovation has its own characteristics, only developing innovations and platforms that distinguish it from other types. In other words, one financial innovation it forces any financial markets to work practically.

The state cannot be left out of mastering and distributing base innovations in the market sector of the economy. It is not for nothing that the state is going to return to a centralized innovation system that will fully take over the planning and financing of base innovations in all areas, as well as improving innovations in most areas. It is in emergency situations, in a mobilizing economy, justified himself in the military-industrial complex, but the initiative of entrepreneurs and undermined responsibility, because in practice the mechanism of competitive struggle, violence

in the promotion of innovation and excluded the harmonization of lubrication policies.

But the base in the market economy, especially the competitiveness of the entire country and the national economy, it turns out inappropriate and safe to download the entire responsibility for mastering and disseminating epochal innovations that determine their effectiveness and safety to entrepreneurs. Such innovationalr will usually have a long-term and high-risk character across the network, while entrepreneurs will not like it very much. In addition, base innovations require large and long-term investments with a large self-coverage period, and this is usually not capable of entrepreneurs, especially those who have suffered from a stretched crisis and the size of the tax burden.

Therefore, the state has already taken over the initial investment in the acquisition of new generation techniques (technology) - in cooperation with enterprises, gradually increasing their share and transferring the flow of improving financial innovations to their disposal. This is especially important for public sector enterprises, which are directly responsible for the effectiveness and competitiveness of their activities.

Financial innovation should contribute to the development of business and innovative infrastructure. These two areas of activity are closely linked. Foreign experiments and, in a sense, local experiments show that small enterprises are "intelligence officers" who master new areas for innovative activities; they are followed by the main force - Capital, which carries out strategic innovative growth. Innovative infrastructure, in favor of this, at the same time through it is considered a kind of bridge, through which the achievements of Science and technology take a difficult path towards production.

Training of personnel for financial innovation growth - buvosita is the subject of state care. Here we are talking about the innovative direction of higher and secondary-special education, as well as the system of training, retraining and distance learning, as well as specialized training and training of small innovative

businesses for specific innovative programs and projects. Rejuvenation of the personnel structure of scientists, constructors, Engineers requires special attention; here there is an increase in middle-aged people and conservatism, little youth is entering this area. The research, design and engineering foundations of the defense-industrial sector have been significantly undermined.

In the real integration of higher education institutions, which are considered the basis in the provision of personnel of financial innovation growth, innovative active enterprises, academic and network institutions, natural growth of youth flow are taking place. Such integration-more consortium than organizational and economic unification, strategic technological alliances, etc.k. in the form of organization - first of all, it is advisable to implement in the priority areas of innovative growth.

The protection and regulation of the Justice Agency for financial innovation, its use inside the country and abroad is an important area of state financial innovation activity. Gap intellectual product (inventions, utility models, industrial samples, achievements in selection, applications for exposure, integrated circuit topologies, data sets, etc.k.) at the expense of which funds and whose balance - the creative person, enterprise, municipal, regional or federal budget - will go about the effective use of important parts of the country's innovative wealth, regardless of which. While carrying out the evaluation and examination of applications for inventions, the state patent authority will allocate the most promising and effective within them, helping to patent them in the Republic and abroad (including financial support), their promotion to the use in enterprises of all forms of ownership to create a completely new product or technology, the income from the sale of inventions must determine the procedure for distribution in all partners-inventors, enterprises and the State pass.

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